

THE IMPORTANCE OF SOIL DATA UNIFICATION FROM SERBIAN AGRICULTURAL ADVISORY SERVICE AND ACCOMPANYING PROBLEMS

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Abstract

A huge amount of soil data represents potentially useful information for soil mapping. Therefore, in many parts of the world, great efforts are being made to preserve, harmonize and use the data acquired in the previous period. Problem occurs when original data are burdened with various errors that occurred during their collection and digitization. In order to make them useful, unification of data is required. The purpose of this study was to make the base for large scale territory mapping. Therefore, 1,200,000 soil data obtained from 200,000 soil samples, from Agricultural advisory services of the Republic of Serbia, (AASS) were harmonized and used for mapping the territory of Central Serbia. The coordinate system or projection is considered as the main parameter according to unification was done. The main obstacles during unification were in sorting over five different coordinate systems per file, aligning headers, rows and columns that will be converted to CSV format to load data into GIS mapping software. Only after unification, vector and raster layers were created, merged and compared to other sources. Maps show the distribution of seven soil properties: pH in water, pH in KCl, CaCO₃, soil organic matter (SOM), total N, P₂O₅ and K₂O. These maps (data) compared with the future maps could contribute an insight into the balance of nutrients and SOM, providing information on further tendencies - degradation or enrichment of soil at the state level. Mapping the soil properties over a large-scale territory is important for planning the type and amount of fertilization distribution, amelioration strategies and regionalization in agriculture. Also, with a provided data on the map, we can easily notice parts of the territory where data/analysis is missing and therefore influence additional field and laboratory research in order to obtain more accurate information, which will help the rational use of soil resources. Thus, it is necessary to point out the lack of a protocol for collecting soil data which makes it difficult to enter the obtained data and calls into question their correctness. Adherence to the defined protocol would facilitate the entry of all collected data into a single soil database, which would provide a powerful tool for various spatial analyses of soils in Serbia. Solutions that would contribute to all of the above is that all AASS use one coordinate system or projection when sampling and use same methodology in soil analyses.

Keywords: GIS, AASS, mapping